

Migrating ORDS Deployment to GitOps

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

The CERN IT department offers hosting of custom applications running on Oracle databases. These services require specific configuration files for managing the settings and to ensure correct deployment.

Previously, these services were configured using a system management tool called DaDEdit. In 2021, a REST API implementation of the DaDEdit Tool known as ORDS Module was introduced to emulate the functionalities of the tool.

Although the ORDS module successfully generates the configuration files; however, certain functionalities such as **customization** of these files still require usage of the DaDEdit Tool.

The main goal of this project is to transfer the customization of configuration files currently available via DaDEdit - to configuration files which can be stored and managed in a version control system such as Git.

The main steps in this project are :

- Redesigning the configuration backend from the database to the local filesystem.
- Replacing the DaDEdit tool by adding features in the existing ORDS module; namely, to use local data files to generate configuration files.
- Creating a new module specifically for generating configuration files through locally edited files.

ABSTRACT

DaDEdit is a system tool used to manage configuration files for custom CERN applications. This project focuses on experimenting with a GitOps based approach to system management as an alternative to DaDEdit.

In this project, remaining functionalities of DaDEdit - such as customization of configuration files is implemented in the Rest API implementation of DaDEdit, known as the ORDS Module. A new python module is specifically created for generating the customized configuration files using locally edited data files, which can then be stored and managed in a version control system like Git.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION	05
---------------------	-----------

EXISTING ARCHITECTURE	06
------------------------------	-----------

IMPLEMENTED SOLUTION	07
-----------------------------	-----------

CONCLUSION	10
-------------------	-----------

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	10
------------------------	-----------

REFERENCES	10
-------------------	-----------

1. INTRODUCTION

The IT-PW-ARW (IT- Platforms & Workflows - Applications & Reusable Workflows) group at CERN provides Platforms as a Service (PaaS). As part of the group, the JEEDY team uses Kubernetes based tools for deployment and maintenance of custom CERN services, hosted on Oracle databases.

ORDS (Oracle Rest Data Services) [1] is a middleware Java application used to bridge the gap between these services and Oracle databases. The IT-PW-ARW group provides hosting for many services including EDH, EDMS and the CERN Phonebook.

All the services belong to one of the following types :

- APEX
- ORAWEB
- ORDS

The type of the service provides information about the settings required for it. For example, Database Access Descriptors (DaDs) of APEX based applications have 4 schemas, ORAWEB has 1 and ORDS has 2 schemas. The details of these services and their corresponding DaDs and schemas are stored in **configuration files** (config files).

These service-specific config files are generated using a system management tool called DaDEdit. Owing to infrastructural changes, this tool is only available to system managers. The tool has been known to be prone to mistakes by users and is highly inconvenient to use.

Efforts have been made to replace DaDEdit with better alternatives. In 2021, to offset the troublesome usage of DaDEdit, a custom REST API known as ORDS module [2] was developed; which provides the same functionality of generating configuration files as the DaDEdit tool. However, DaDEdit is still required to edit (customize) the configuration files for any changes. Therefore, there exists a need for an alternative workflow to customize and manage different versions of the configuration files deployed in the Kubernetes clusters.

The project aims to introduce GitOps [3] - a way of implementing Continuous Deployment for cloud based applications. Integrating GitOps allows management & deployment of files with ease - committing the changes in the git repository updates and syncs the changes in the Kubernetes clusters through an automated process.

Within the context of the project, GitOps facilitates editing configuration files without the DaDEdit tool, and tracking changes through Git. Building on the previous work, the project also aims to emulate the remaining functionality provided by DaDEdit, replacing the tool in its entirety.

2. Existing Architecture

The current architecture consists of the ORDS module present as a docker image repository. This image repository generates configuration and war files required for ORDS based on data provided by the dadEdit3 database, through API requests.

The repository script runs inside an init container in Kubernetes and the generated configuration files are passed on to a Tomcat pod and then the service is updated with the settings. Figure 1 provides an overview of the current workflow.

Figure 1 : *Current Architecture workflow for updating the service webpage*

Both the DaDEdit tool and its API implementation - ORDS Module, use the database to generate the config files. Therefore, to generate new config files, edits have to be made to the data files - which currently could only be done through DaDEdit.

A simple alternative is to download the required data files locally, edit them and generate configuration files, thereby bypassing the usage of the DaDEdit tool completely. These changes can then be committed to Git, which can then manage the different versions of the services.

This functionality was achieved in two steps:

1. Redesigning the configuration backend.
2. Creating a new module for generating the configuration files using local data.

3. Implemented Solution

The primary step involved going through the existing codebase of the ORDS module to understand how the configuration files were generated, the structure of those files; and more importantly, what data was required to generate them.

a. Redesigning Configuration Backend

Through the codebase review, 4 kinds of JSON data files were identified and retrieved to generate config files, namely:

- service.json : provides settings about the specific service.
- dad.json : provides settings about the various DaDs of the service.
- schema.json : provides settings about various schemas for each DaD in the service.
- parameter.json : provides descriptions about different settings.

```
{
  "result": [
    {
      "id": 404,
      "name": "CERN_SECRET_SERVICE",
      "context_root": "/found",
      "type": "SSO",
      "clean": "N",
      "frozen": "N",
      "cluster_name": null,
      "entity": null,
      "frontend_entity": null,
      "application_name": "lhc",
      "redeploy": "N",
      "config_refresh": "N",
      "ords_version": "127.0.0.1",
      "p1": null,
      "p2": null,
      "p3": null,
      "p4": null,
      "p5": "true",
      "p6": "5",
      "p7": "20",
      "p8": "true",
      "p9": null,
      "p10": "true"
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 2 : Dummy representation of JSON Data for a Service

Note that each service requires these 4 types of JSON data to generate the config files. Also, all data files contain unique & specific settings for a given service.

To redesign the configuration backend, a feature was implemented in the ORDS Module to download the relevant data files for a given service. These local data files can then be used to generate the configuration files (Figure 3).

Figure 3 : *Redesigning configuration backend from Database to Local System*

The feature allows for generalized usage for any service with command line flags. There are presently 3 ways of using the script :

1. NO FLAG

If no flag is provided as a command line argument, the script executes as was done previously; i.e. configuration files are generated using API calls to the database. No data files are downloaded.

2. WEBSERVICE FLAG

The WEBSERVICE Flag downloads the relevant JSON data files of a given service. The directory to store the downloaded JSON files can also be specified. The local data files are then used to generate the configuration files.

3. LOCAL_FILES FLAG

The LOCAL_FILES flag solely uses local data files to generate the configuration files. These data files can be edited and the new configuration files are generated. The directory where the data files are stored in the local system has to be specified.

Note that if some relevant data files are missing, the script will log an error and exit. The missing data files can be downloaded using the WEBSERVICE Flag.

For each of the flags, the configuration files will be generated in the Output folder which can be specified as well.

A validation script was written to compare the configuration files generated using the existing ORDS Module and the new feature which used local data files. The configuration outputs matched successfully.

b. New Module for generating configuration files using local data.

Since the configuration files are only updated infrequently, a new module was created, exclusively focused on using local data for their generation. A couple of features in the module include:

- No usage of the DaDEdit tool or any instance of database.
- Command line arguments (flags) are not needed for the module.
- Flexible mount arguments for data and output folders.
- Decoupled extra binaries and removed stored war files from the repository, reducing repository size.
- Added functionality for downloading war files dynamically based on the ORDS version to the image container.
- Refactored and removed redundant code based on the previous module.
- Improved logging and debug messages to build a robust script.

Figure 4 : *Generating Configuration files using local JSON data.*

The edited local files are inputted into the new module to generate the configuration files. These configuration files can be stored in Git. If the generated files break the service, the config file version can easily be rolled back to a previous working instance. The project was therefore successful in replacing the DaDEdit tool with a GitOps based - system management approach.

4. CONCLUSION

This project proves to be a promising proof of concept for adopting GitOps values. The features added in the existing ORDS module and the new python module allows us to finally replace DaDEdit and introduce GitOps as a management system.

A favorable future step will be to integrate the current solution with continuous delivery tools like ArgoCD. Thus, a user can customize the settings of a service by :

- Downloading relevant data files from the ORDS module.
- Editing the files locally and using the new module to generate configuration files.
- These configuration files will then be pushed to Git - and the version history will be stored.
- This change will be detected by the ArgoCD pipeline, the configuration files will be updated and redeployed to the service.

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6. REFERENCES

- [1] Oracle ORDS: <https://www.oracle.com/database/technologies/appdev/rest.html>
- [2] ORDS Module Project Report by Marcel Ochsendorf : <https://zenodo.org/record/5541651>
- [3] GitOps : <https://www.gitops.tech/>
- [4] Link to ORDS Module : <https://gitlab.cern.ch/jeedy/utils/ords-config-image>
- [5] Link to new Python Module : <https://gitlab.cern.ch/jeedy/utils/ords-config-image-local>

